

"Constant Curvature of a sphere and a pseudosphere"

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1.0 Constant curvature

There are zonal area similarities and equalities between a sphere and a pseudosphere. These equivalences are seen using geometrical methods in revolution surfaces of Gaussian constant total curvature and constant Delaunay curvature. In demonstrating these equivalences and tracing the identified surface profiles, a bicycle wheels as cycloids limiting the profiles.

A pseudosphere has the same volume as a normal sphere as well as a constant negative Gaussian curvature as compared to a sphere which has a positive one, a property that gives it its name (Apostol and Mamikon, 2016). A pseudosphere is named so due to the many comparable properties it shares with a sphere concerning curvature. It is also referred to as the tractricoid, antisphere, tractrisoid or tractroid. The only difference is that a sphere has a constant positive Gaussian curvature while an invariable negative Gaussian curving characterizes a pseudosphere. Notably, a pseudosphere and a sphere have several equalities and similarities, including the fact that the surface area of a pseudosphere is calculated by $4\pi k^2$ from an integral calculus, which is the same as sphere surface area of radius k , derived at by rotating a circle about the diameter (Taioli et al., 2016). In the case of a pseudosphere, this radius is therefore referred to as a pseudoradius. Another two-dimensional analogous relationship exists between a sphere circular disk and a tractrix. The area that connects the two full tractrices has an equal area to circular disk area of radius k .

1.2 Surface Area Theorem

Following the existing analogies on the sphere surfaces, a pseudosphere, a theorem is developed out of the relationship from the zone by zone area property. The theorem states that if an antisphere with pseudo radius k is subdivided into zones using right angles planes about the asymptote, lateral surface area of each zone being equivalent to that of a analogous zone on a circular cylinder of radius k and thus also on a spherical zone of radius k . notably, a sphere's surface area is equivalent to that of a pseudosphere.

2.0 Constant Gaussian curvature surfaces

The zone surface area equalities on a solid sphere and a pseudosphere are extendable to zone surface areas on any revolution surface of constant Gaussian curvature, whether negative or positive. The property implies that every spherical member of the family with constant curvatures are the same. This analysis is also applied to revolution solids of constant negative curvature. The same also applies to all pseudospherical members of this family as they have equal zonal areas on surfaces of constant negative curvature.

2.1 Definition

2.1.1 Sphere: Gaussian plane curvature equal to $1/a^2$

Polar parameterization :

$$\begin{cases} z = a \int_0^t \sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 u} \, du = aE(k, t) \\ \rho = ak \cos t \end{cases}$$

1st Fundamental form (quadratic):

$$(ds)^2 = (d\rho)^2 + \rho^2 (d\theta)^2$$

Curvature meridian radius:

$$R_{cm} = a \frac{\sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 t}}{k \cos t}$$

Curvature parallel radius:

$$R_{cp} = a \frac{k \cos t}{\sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 t}}$$

Gaussian curvature:

$$K = \frac{1}{R_{cm} R_{cp}} = \frac{1}{a^2}$$

Mean curvature:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_{cm}} + \frac{1}{R_{cp}} \right) = \frac{1 + k^2 \cos 2t}{2k \cos t \sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 t}}$$

The above derivation is applicable to all surfaces of a sphere.

2.2 Gaussian Curvature $-1/a^2$

2.2.1 Conical:

$$\begin{cases} z = a \int_0^t \sqrt{1 - k^2 \operatorname{ch}^2 u} \, du \\ \rho = ak \operatorname{sh} t \end{cases} \quad 0 < k < 1$$

1st fundamental quadratic form

$$(ds)^2 = (d\rho)^2 + \rho^2 (d\theta)^2$$

Curvature Meridian radius

$$R_{cm} = -a \frac{\sqrt{1 - k^2 \text{sh}^2 t}}{k \text{cht}}$$

Parallel curvature radius:

$$R_{cp} = a \frac{k \text{cht}}{\sqrt{1 - k^2 \text{sh}^2 t}}$$

Gaussian curvature:

$$K = \frac{1}{R_{cm} R_{cp}} = -\frac{1}{a^2}$$

The mean curvature is;

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_{cm}} + \frac{1}{R_{cp}} \right)$$

2.2.2 hyperboloid

Polar parametrization:

$$\begin{cases} z = a \int_0^t \sqrt{1 - k^2 \text{sh}^2 u} \, du = -iaE(-k, it) \\ \rho = ak \text{cht} \end{cases} \quad (\text{for any } k \text{ value})$$

1st fundamental form

$$(ds)^2 = (d\rho)^2 + \rho^2 (d\theta)^2$$

Meridian radius;

$$R_{cm} = -a \frac{\sqrt{1 - k^2 \operatorname{ch}^2 t}}{k \operatorname{sh} t}$$

Parallel radius:

$$R_{cp} = a \frac{k \operatorname{sh} t}{\sqrt{1 - k^2 \operatorname{ch}^2 t}}$$

Gaussian curvature;

$$K = \frac{1}{R_{cm} R_{cp}} = -\frac{1}{a^2}$$

Mean curvature:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_{cm}} + \frac{1}{R_{cp}} \right)$$

In the case of a pseudosphere, the above surfaces apply.

The meridian radius of the curvature of a revolution surface is equal to that of the surface profile. In contrast, the parallel radius of curvature equals the segment line length on the body to the normal and axis intersection.

2.2.3 Pseudosphere

Whereas it has a constant positive Gaussian curvature, an antisphere has an invariable negative curve of its surface revolution about the asymptote generated by a tractrix.

The Cartesian parametric equations are;

$$\cos v \operatorname{sech} u = x$$

$$\sin v \operatorname{sech} u = y$$

$$u - \tanh u = z$$

The implicit Cartesian form can be written as

$$z^2 = \left[a \operatorname{sech}^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a}} \right) - \sqrt{a^2 - x^2 - y^2} \right]^2.$$

Other parameterizations include

$$\sin v \cos u = x$$

$$\sin v \sin u = y$$

$$\cos v + \ln[\tan(1/2v)] = z$$

For $u \in [0, 2\pi)$ and $v \in (0, \pi)$

$$X = \varphi(v) \cos u$$

$$Y = \varphi(v) \sin u$$

$$Z = \psi(v)$$

For $u \in [0, 2\pi)$ and $v \in (-\infty, \infty)$, where

$$\varphi(v) = \begin{cases} e^v & \text{for } v < 0 \\ e^{-v} & \text{for } v \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\psi(v) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{1 - e^{2v}} - \tanh^{-1}(\sqrt{1 - e^{2v}}) & \text{for } v < 0 \\ \ln(e^v + \sqrt{e^{2v} - 1}) - e^{-v} \sqrt{e^{2v} - 1} & \text{for } v \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

In the first parametrization, the coefficients of the 1st elementary form are as follows

$$e = \tanh^2 u$$

$$f = 0$$

$$g = \operatorname{sech}^2 u,$$

The coefficients in the 2nd basic form are;

$$E = -\operatorname{sech} u \tanh u$$

$$F=0$$

$$G = \operatorname{sech} u \tanh u,$$

The element of the surface is as follows

$$dS = \operatorname{sech} u \tanh u.$$

The surface is, therefore;

$$S = 2 \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \operatorname{sech} u \tanh u \, du \, dv = 4\pi,$$

A Pseudosphere has a finite volume even though it has an infinite extent. The volume is calculated by changing the variables $z = u - \tanh u$ to give $dz = \tanh^2 u \, du$ and replacing it into the revolution solid equation to give;

$$V = \pi \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \operatorname{sech}^2 u \tanh^2 u \, du = \frac{2}{3} \pi,$$

This is also equivalent to that of a normal sphere. Gaussian curving is provided through;

$$K = -1$$

$$H = \frac{1}{2}(\sinh u - \operatorname{csch} u).$$

The pseudosphere, as seen above, has the same volume as that of a usual sphere while having an invariable negative Gaussian curving and not an invariable positive curve as of the standard sphere. The properties result in a pseudosphere. The pseudosphere has an unvarying genitive curving giving it an incomplete frame of hyperbolic geometry as seen in a cone. A cylinder is an incomplete local frame of the Euclidean geometry of the level surface.

The geodesics equation of a pseudosphere is given as follows;

$$\cosh^2 u + (v + c)^2 = k^2.$$

3.0 Main Result

A pseudosphere is a revolution surface derived from rotating a tractrix about the asymptote. A tractrix, being a flat surface curve, has such properties as its tangent segment

between the contact spot and a permanent plane straight line has a constant length of a .

Therefore, concerning a tractrix, a pseudosphere is given through;

$$X(a, u) = [a(\cos u + \frac{1}{n} \tan u/2), a \sin u \sin v, a \sin u \cos v]$$

From the computations, it can be deduced that the invariable Gaussian curve for the pseudosphere and sphere is $K = a^{-2}$, and $K = -a^{-2}$, respectively. The following corollary can, therefore, be stated.

A surface with a constant positive Gaussian curving $K = a^{-2}$ is a local isomer of a sphere with a radius a , and exterior plane with a negative unvarying Gaussian curving $K = -a^{-2}$ is a local isomer to a pseudosphere.

In closed surfaces, the Gaussian curvature is studied using a different metric referred to as the piecewise linear metric. Piecewise linear metric is characterized by flatness everywhere except on finite point sets where conical singularities are developed. If the surface is triangulated with the vertices, set V containing all the conical singularities and every edge $e \in E$, geodesic. The length of the edges defines the piecewise linear metric such that $E \rightarrow R > 0$.

In the case of vertex $i \in V$ with α_i denoting the angle of the cone at i , the function is the angel defect as follows;

$$W: V \rightarrow R, W_i = 2\pi - \alpha_i.$$

Taking S to be a closed surface for the piecewise flat metric d , and V being the finite set that contains d conical singularities, the discrete Gaussian curvature at the vertex is equivalent to the quotient area A_i of its Voronoi cell at I and the angle defect W_i .

Theorem

There is a discrete conformally equivalent piecewise linear metric for each piecewise linear metric d , such that its surface has a constant discrete Gaussian curvature. Rocek,

Williams, and Luo established the concept of distinct conformal equivalence on piecewise flat surfaces with fixed triangulation, which is a straightforward way of discretizing conformal equivalence in smooth surfaces. Riemannian metrics g and $\tilde{g}$ on S surface are equivalent only when there is a conformal factor $u \in C^\infty S$ in such a way that

$$\tilde{g} = e^{2u} g.$$

Two metrics of piecewise linearity on a surface that has fixed triangulation have discrete conformally equivalent when the lengths of their edges $E \rightarrow \mathbb{R} > 0$ are related using a conformal factor $u: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$L_{ij} = \exp(u_i + u_j/2) L_{ij}$$

For the theorem-proof, there is a need for a developed machinery generalization for piecewise flat surfaces with fixed triangulation. Bobenko et al. (2011) showed that the general setting of the problem emanates from hyperbolic geometry, which is essential in explaining the link between decorated, ideal hyperbolic polyhedra, and piecewise flat surfaces the significance of the right setting.

The constant curvature metric $\tilde{d}$ from the theorem is generally not unique but unique in such cases as;

$$V = 1$$

$$S \text{ genus} = 1$$

$$\text{And } S \text{ genus} = 0 \text{ and } V = 3.$$

The constant curvature metric is not unique when S is of Zero genus, and V is four, and if S is of 2 genus and $V = 2$. A thorough analysis is done of the class structure and related triangulations to prove the uniqueness of constant curvature metrics using constant discrete Gaussian curvature in the discrete conformal sphere classes.

4.0 References

Apostol, Tom M., and Mamikon A. Mnatsakanian. "A New Look at Surfaces of Constant Curvature." *The American Mathematical Monthly* 123.5 (2016): 439-447.

Taioli, Simone, et al. "Lobachevsky crystallography made real through carbon pseudospheres." *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* 28.13 (2016): 13LT01.